

Recommended citation: Aerts, C., Buijs, J., Truwant, M., & Haenen, C. (2018). (Re)integrating long term unemployed engineers through innovation projects. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 521-530). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672611.

(Re)integrating long term unemployed engineers through innovation projects

C. Aerts

Project Officer

KU Leuven – Faculty of Engineering Technology
Leuven, Belgium

E-mail: celine.aerts@kuleuven.be

J. Buijs

Program director postgraduate programmes

KU Leuven - Faculty of Engineering Technology
Leuven, Belgium

E-mail: jeroen.buijs@kuleuven.be

M. Truwant

Project Officer (former)

KU Leuven – Faculty of Engineering Technology
Leuven, Belgium

E-mail: mirjam.truwant@kuleuven.be

C. Haenen

Coordinator corporate relations

KU Leuven - Faculty of Engineering Technology
Leuven, Belgium

E-mail: chrisje.haenen@kuleuven.be

Conference Key Areas: University-Business cooperation, Continuing EE and Lifelong Learning, Recruitment and Retention

Keywords: Long term unemployment, dual learning, engineering, Flanders

INTRODUCTION

The Flemish labour market for engineers is marked by a striking paradox of both scarcity and growing unemployment. Looking at numbers provided by VDAB (Flemish Service for Employment and Vocational Training), we see that on the one hand an increasing number of vacancies for engineers is not filled (at the end of August 2016, 3942 vacancies were open [1]), while on the other hand more and more engineers are registered as job-seekers (in the same period there were 2248). In three years' time there is even a tripling of the engineering shortage (from 2214 vacancies at the end of 2013 to 4120 at the end of 2016). The actual shortage is probably even larger, as not all vacancies are registered with VDAB by companies.

Especially over-50s and immigrants are having a hard time (re)integrating into the labour market. For both groups the chances of recruitment are higher when competencies can be demonstrated through workplace learning or internships. Add to this the fact that long-term unemployed engineers need a knowledge update (as their knowledge is obsolete and/or because they have to look further than the domain in which they have specialized for many years), and the principle of dual learning emerges. That concept of dual learning can be applied to all long-term job seekers.

In September 2016 a follow-up project for the Postgraduate Programme in Innovation & Entrepreneurship in engineering was approved by VLAIO (Agency Flanders Innovation & Entrepreneurship). One of the additional goals of the project was exactly this (re)integration of unemployed engineers. The programme is a cooperation between all Flemish universities, and very early during the process, a partnership agreement with VDAB was signed for this project. Representatives from all universities and VDAB formed a project team and named the pilot project WINWIN ("Werkzoekende INgenieurs Werken aan INnovatie"). The pilot project took place in academic year 2017-2018.

1 GENERAL

1.1 Dual learning in Flanders

The large discrepancy between increasing scarcity of engineers and increased unemployment in the engineering sector calls for a solution that better matches supply and demand. A possible answer is contained in the concept of dual learning.

With the Concept Note bis [2], the Flemish government decided in 2015 to focus on dual learning as a fully qualified learning pathway in secondary education. Through dual learning, i.e. a learning trajectory that deals with work experience and a related learning component, education and the professional field are brought closer together. This movement enables a qualification process that is closely in line with the reality of the workplace, thus facilitating competency matching in the labour market. With the decree concerning dual learning [3] the Flemish government explicitly states the ambition to extend the dual learning line to be extended to higher education in order to further bridge the gap between education and the labour market.

1.2 Dual learning and unemployment in Flanders

For the (re)employment of specific target groups in unemployment, workplace learning, whether or not in combination with customised further training, can also be a suitable approach. Several recent initiatives illustrate how this is already being done in practice among the lower educated. For example, the VDAB concept of “Intensive Workplace Learning” offers long-term unemployed people vocational training within the social economy; WELT, a VOKA initiative in collaboration with VDAB, tries to fill bottleneck vacancies within the framework of corporate social responsibility by means of work experience and learning pathways; and finally, VDAB also sets up entry placements for young unemployed people without a higher diploma. These concepts can, subject to adaptation, be transferred to a highly educated target audience.

In the context of job-seeking engineers, such a programme can consist of a combination of a work placement, in which knowledge is updated in line with the latest technological developments, and a supplementary course, in which both (broad) technical competencies and soft skills are central. This training course will enable job-seekers to fill certain skills gaps and, in addition, to gain up-to-date workplace experience that will make it easier for them to (re)find a job.

1.3 Dual learning for long term unemployed engineers

Flanders, and by extension Belgium, is obviously not the only region where the labour market for engineers is characterised by the apparent contradiction between a serious shortage of engineers and an increasing group of job seekers with precisely that qualification. It is therefore also worth looking beyond national borders when seeking a suitable approach to resolving this discrepancy. In Germany, for example, the cradle of dual learning, three different (re-)employment projects were rolled out in the period 1991-2009, one by one based on the principle of cooperation between university institutions and industry.

A first project is mentioned in the article 'A practice-based model for continued engineering education' (1991) [4]. The model described here combines a company-based, interdisciplinary team project with technical courses that fit within an individual training programme.

In the period 1999 - 2002, another rehabilitation project, 'Arbeitslose Ingenieure in den ersten Arbeitsmarkt' [5], was launched. Here three actors (the University of Magdeburg, the employment service in Magdeburg and the company Bosch in Feuerbach) joined forces to coordinate demand (a large engineering deficit in the mechanical engineering sector in the Stuttgart region) and supply (a historically high number of unemployed engineers in the Magdeburg region). Engineers specialising in mechanical engineering initially followed a four-month course in the automotive sector, while simultaneously acquiring soft skills, computer skills and technical English via workshops. This was followed by a 6-month internship at Bosch (Feuerbach, Stuttgart). Over a period of 3 years, 50 to 60 engineers were reemployed in this way.

A third and last German project, return2job [6], (2008-2010) aimed to reintegrate engineers who, due to family commitments, had not been active for many years into the labour market, through technical and scientific training via distance learning (40 - 60 ECTS), soft skills seminars and three months of work experience. The companies that offered an internship evaluated the internship well to very well, and half of the participants were employed within six months of the end of the internship.

Also further away, dual learning projects are developing. Canada, which has an active immigration policy, offers an 'Engineering and Technology Upgrading Program' [7] in the state of Alberta for engineers trained abroad who do not yet have Canadian work experience. The programme includes soft skills training for the Canadian context, an upgrade of technical/technological competencies, an AutoCAD training course and a workplace experience within an engineering company in Calgary. According to the own data of this programme, 97% of the participants succeed in being employed as engineers at the end of the programme.

2 WINWIN PROJECT

2.1 Project design

In September 2016, VLAIO approved a follow-up project for the "Postgraduate Programme in Innovation & Entrepreneurship in engineering". This postgraduate programme [8] is a joint initiative of faculties of the five Flemish universities that offer programmes in industrial sciences, biosciences, bioengineering and engineering sciences, and it aims to ensure that students are better prepared for the practice of their profession by focusing on the development of innovation, entrepreneurial and professional competences, aside from technical engineering skills. Within this follow-up project, a number of new objectives were formulated, of which involving job-seeking engineers was one.

VDAB is the public employment service of Flanders, and thus functions an important partner in the project. Very early during the process, a partnership agreement was signed between the universities and VDAB.

During the WINWIN-project, the unemployed engineer participates in a so-called 'innovation project'. An innovation project is a company project aimed at the development and implementation of a product, process, service or concept that is new and innovative for the company. This is done under the guidance of a company mentor, and a university coach.

Based on the present and desired competence profile of the individual participant, the mentor can decide on maximum two additional courses that have to be followed at the universities. Naturally, this decision is made in consultation with the participant, the company mentor and university coach.

Depending on the individual upgrade process, the duration of the project is between 12 and 16 weeks, with approximately 60 working days (3 to 5 working days per week). During the duration of the project, the unemployed engineer still receives his unemployment benefits.

2.2 Selection procedure

The postgraduate programme has a lot of experience with the coordination of innovation projects and can thus count on a large corporate network. Companies from the internship database of the postgraduate programme were contacted and asked about their interest in WINWIN. After mostly positive responses, the project team started the recruitment procedure for candidates.

The target group consists of all job-seeking engineers with a master's degree in Flanders who have been job-seeking for at least one year and are registered with VDAB. A targeted mailing was carried out by VDAB and flyers and posters were distributed. Additionally, a brand new website was launched (winwinproject.be [9]). By June 2017, these marketing efforts led to a total of 43 candidates that applied for the WINWIN pilot project through the website.

The selection process that followed consisted of three steps, namely a pre-screening procedure, a round of interviews and finally a finalising selection meeting. The pre-screening and selection interviews were intended to provide clarity about a candidate's attitude, soft-skills, and technical competencies. After all, a suitable candidate must have a minimum of competencies. There are therefore initial terms that must be fulfilled.

The pre-screening of suitable candidates was carried out by local VDAB consultants who, on the one hand, had to check whether a candidate met the hard criteria (engineering diploma at master level and looking for work for at least a year) and, on the other hand, could assess the attitude and potential of the candidate, regardless of his/her technical knowledge. Following this pre-screening process, the number of candidates was reduced from 42 to 35.

For the round of interviews, those 35 people were invited for an interview of half an hour, with the aim of selecting 10 suitable candidates. Each selection committee consisted of at least four people, namely a HR professional specialised in the recruitment of engineers, a lecturer with a background in engineering education, the regional coordinator of the postgraduate programme and a representative of the VDAB. The interviews were conducted in accordance with a common script. In the end, 32 interviews were held, from which 12 people were selected.

2.3 Participants

For the twelve selected candidates, the search for a suitable business match commenced. An overview can be found in *table 1*.

Table 1: Overview of the participants of the WINWIN project

No.	Sex	Age	Region
1	M	41-50	East Flanders
2	M	31-40	Antwerp
3	M	31-40	Antwerp
4	M	51-60	East Flanders
5	M	51-60	West Flanders
6	M	51-60	Antwerp
7	M	51-60	Flemish Brabant
8	F	31-40	Limburg
9	F	31-40	East Flanders
10	M	41-50	Antwerp
11	F	51-60	Flemish Brabant
12	F	51-60	Flemish Brabant
13	M	51-60	Antwerp
14	M	51-60	Limburg

For three participants (order no.: 1-3), the WINWIN project was already a success before they started the innovation project. During the search for a suitable project these participants already found a job. Two of these contacts came about as a result of the WINWIN project.

For two other participants (order no.: 4-5), the search proved to be a lot more difficult. It became clear that there were motivation and/or attitude problems that had not come to the fore during the selection procedure. For them, the WINWIN project was therefore terminated. Two new participants were then picked up from the reserve list (order no: 13-14). Unfortunately, we were unable to find a suitable innovation project for them in time, so they did not complete the project.

A match between a project and the profile of the participant was found for the other seven participants (order no: 6-12).

3 EVALUATION PROJECT

3.1 Main findings

Of the seven participants who started the WINWIN project, two have currently found a job, approximately three months after the end of the internship. One of the participants was offered a contract with her internship company. Furthermore, even before the project started, two candidates were able to work through contacts made by the WINWIN coach. A total of four long-term job-seeking engineers were put to work by the WINWIN project.

3.2 Conclusions

3.2.1 *Attitude, motivation and professional skills*

There is a clear need for coaching on attitude, motivation and professional skills, but the current set-up of the programme does not sufficiently meet these needs: experience learns that there are almost always underlying reasons why the participants can't find a job (attitude, psychological, communication, etc.). As an additional complication, it turns out that job seekers are often very reluctant to undergo attitude training because they themselves do not see the need for it.

The current partnership of engineering faculties, assisted by the VDAB, reflects this initial choice: it can rely on assets such as a large industrial network and the capacity to provide a (bio)technological knowledge update, but the expertise needed to work specifically on the listed problem areas is lacking. To overcome these hurdles, a next edition will take this double solution into account:

1. Not let all (potential) candidates immediately participate in the internship, but to provide the option for some of them, after the first intake interview, to first follow a general "skills" trajectory;
2. Expand the consortium with additional partners (e.g. career centres, outplacement agencies...) who can complete this person-centred coaching.

3.2.2 *Role of the coaches*

From the start of the project it became clear that the supervision of WINWIN participants required a different approach than regular postgraduate students: the selection of suitable candidates (intake interviews) proved to be time-consuming, and during the course of the project they needed a much closer and more intensive follow-up - both by the coaches and by VDAB. The topics that had to be discussed with the candidates were often different from those that were discussed with the regular students. Moreover, it was much more difficult to find a good business match for the candidates, so more time needs to be set aside for this in the future.

And finally: a relationship of trust between coach and coachee is very important. Experience shows, however, that some candidates - certainly in the beginning - are suspicious of the coaches of the universities, perhaps because of the close link that exists with the VDAB. As a result, important information is not shared with the coach, or is shared only at a late stage. That is why in the future it is important that the roles remain effectively separated but also that they are communicated more transparently to participants.

3.2.3 *Knowledge update via courses from the university offer*

Participants of the WINWIN project often take one or two university courses (n=5). Although the participants are very enthusiastic about the courses and indicate that

they can immediately apply the content of the courses in the internship, they indicate that passing the exam is too difficult. For a follow-up project, examinations should be more encouraged or even made compulsory.

3.2.4 Internship

The project foresees that participants in the WINWIN project as well as those in the postgraduate programme in principle participate in an 'innovation' project. In practice, however, the internships of the WINWIN participants are often of an operational nature: an innovative path is, in this phase of their career, often too ambitious. In the future, the project should therefore explicitly allow for operational internships, while ensuring that they remain 'engineering' projects.

Whereas in the initial pilot project this was not yet well enough coordinated and in some cases led to frustrations, in a new project the employment possibilities in the future will have to be taken even more into account in the search for a suitable internship. For example, concrete vacancies can be used, or there will have to be clear communication between the internship company and the participant about possible employment afterwards.

3.2.5 Information flow within the consortium

The partners each have a very partial view of a candidate's competence profile - and their skill gaps. In the future, it should be possible to exchange information on this subject in a more structured way, taking into account, of course, the principles of privacy.

3.3 Future

In September 2018 a second pilot phase ("WINWIN project 2.0") will be launched, based on the conclusions reached in the initial project. It will give the project a new interpretation, while retaining its original objectives. In order to reach these objectives, a preparatory phase will be built into pilot project 2.0. This means that not all participants immediately partake in the company internship, but rather that some participants will first follow a general skills track, consisting of attitude, soft skills and business readiness training. A special focus will be given to career coaching, self-reflection and life skill coaching. An external partner will be in charge of this preparatory track and it will consist of individual coaching, supplemented by group coaching. Whether or not the participant will have a need for this track, will be decided after the first intake interview and after a obligatory three-day workshop organised by VDAB, are completed.

Furthermore, participants will no longer be required to work on an "innovation project", but as of now can also opt for a more operational project. The internships will be chosen with a special focus on the employment possibilities in the future.

The pilot project has provided everyone involved in the WINWIN project with better insight into the complexity of problems that come with long-term job seeking engineers. There is clearly a gap in guidance for these engineers, and many of them would not find a job without help. This again indicates the social importance of the project. The insights gained from the pilot project and the additional insights that will still follow, must be put to practice. It is clear that dual learning and lifelong learning are indispensable for graduate engineers, which should be reflected in the education and organisation of universities and governments.

REFERENCES

- [1] KU Leuven (2016) Eindrapport Studie Ingenieur 2020 [pdf], pp. 14-17, retrieved from https://svl.login.kanooh.be/sites/default/files/atoms/files/conceptnota-bis_duaal_leren_-_een_volwaardige_kwalificerende_leerweg_20150625_def_versie.pdf
- [2] Vlaamse Overheid (2015) Duaal Leren, een volwaardige kwalificerende leerweg - concept nota bis [pdf]
- [3] Vlaamse Overheid (21 maart 2018) Decreet betreffende duaal leren en de aanloopfase [pdf]. Retrieved from <https://www.vlaamsparlement.be/parlementairedocumenten/parlementaire-initiatieven/1231409>
- [4] Theuerkauf W. (1998) 'A practice-based model for continued engineering education [pdf]
- [5] Perl I. (2000) Wiedereinstieg in den Arbeitsmarkt ermöglicht, Retrieved from <http://www.uni-magdeburg.de/unirep/UR2000/januar2000/arbeitslos.html>
- [6] Otto Bennecke Stiftung (2015) Schlussbericht Ergebnissicherung der AQUA-Maßnahmen [pdf]
- [7] X (2016) Engineering and Technology Upgrading Program, Retrieved from <https://www.ccisab.ca/professionals-job-seekers/engineering-and-technology-upgrading-program.html>
- [8] X (2017), Postgraduate Programme in Innovation and Entrepreneurship in Engineering, Retrieved from www.innovationentrepreneurship.be.
- [9] X (2017), WINWIN-project, Retrieved from <http://winwinproject.be/>